

The Contribution of Information Technology to Zara's Success

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Abstract

In this paper, it will be provided a case report for the Zara case. This case report will include the strategies applied by Zara, its competitive advantages, its IT management, and SWOT analysis in the context of which it will be discussed the problems that the company may face. In the last part of this assignment, it will be recommended solutions that are well implementable to resolve potential pitfalls.
Keywords: *IT, Zara's strategy, SWOT analysis, competitive advantages, management, case report, limitations, recommendations*

Introduction

Zara is a Spanish clothing and accessories retail Fashion Company that was founded by Amancio Ortega and Rosalia Mera in 1975. The first appearance of the company in the market was in 1963 when the first Zara's shop opens up in Coruna. Today, the company has 1763 stores in more than 78 countries all over the world and is globally characterized as one of the most innovative and successful companies in the fashion industry.

Literature Review

For the completion of this study, it was used various information resources so as to give an insight into the major issues that this case study arises. Particularly, the data and the evidence provided were retrieved from journal articles, newspapers, and books which dealt with the green principles and strategies. In addition to this, it was found interesting bibliography concerning the strategy that the company follows in order to resolve potential problems and dilemmas.

1. Theoretical framework

The value proposition of Zara demonstrates that the company puts the customer needs in the first place and hence it strives to innovate each time and improve the design and its styles with respect of course, to ethical and environmental issues. In general terms, the cultural values of Zara can be summarized to be perfect, responsible, flexible, having respected to fashion, employees, and teams. All these values showed that Zara does not operate hierarchically but rather horizontally, meaning that the company put great value on building strong teams that can effectively communicate even if other teams located in another country (Lopez, & Fan, 2013). Furthermore, to provide Zara's marketing framework, the company's target customers are primarily people that are fashion-sensitive irrespectively the age and the race. Also, the firm's target markets are in Europe and generally developed and not developing countries. The location of its shops is detected in central areas in which there are many factory shops. Zara's shops create a fashionable atmosphere as the firm adopts a more minimalistic style so that impress customers with its classy and intimate style. Regarding its procurement strategy, Zara develops merchandise sources and relevant strategies to benefit them. Its pricing strategy is a penetrating one, as it offers mediocre quality products at affordable prices with the view of increasing its customer base constantly. What's more, Zara heavily relied on the word-to-mouth method in order to expand its fame across the customers and through opening new stores. Instead, only a little amount of Zara's budget is allocated to advertising. Moreover, Zara's major competitors are Gap, Benetton, and H&M with which they target the same customers. However, it should be admitted that Zara hits the other competitors since it offers more fashionable items at the cheapest price (Bhasin, 2018).

2. Zara's competitive advantages

More analytically, one of the most important strategic advantages of Zara is its agile supply chain, its just-in-time strategy, its “fast fashion” system, its centralized integration system, its in-house production, and the vertical integration system established. Opposed to traditional retailers who focus on the mass production with the view of maintaining the labor costs lower, Zara does not incorporate the outsourcing method into its procurement strategy but rather choose to manufacture products internally (in-housing production). For this reason, the company constructed huge automated factories in which the clothing is manufactured with the contribution of technology advancement and especially robots that have partially replaced the workers who did the manual work in the past. In this way, the firm has the full control of its production and is adequately flexible to manufacture the numbers and the variety of clothes needed so as to attract more customers without enduring excessive inventory costs (Schlossberg, 2016). Furthermore, vertical integration is another important Zara’s characteristic. Launching products in small quantities and applying an effective lean inventory management the company attains to maintain its inventory cost low and formulate a sense of scarcity to its customers with the view to urging them to buy Zara’s clothes immediately after each new collection launched. So, some benefits that derive from this system are that the company saves inventory costs which generally have a detrimental effect on the fashion industry and save time. This attempt is highly facilitated by the fact that Zara applied the “fast fashion” system combined with its just-in-time strategy and its short-lead time. These policies entail that the company does not wait the fashion season to launch new products, but every 10-14 days launched a new collection so as to avoid fashion risks and be able to keep pace with the ever-changing fashion industry (Dutta, 2002). Additionally, Zara has its own supply chain; something that makes the distribution of its product more effective since the company has the flexibility to direct sent its products to stores without delays. As a matter of fact, the value of its supply chains lies in the fact that it helps the company to be consistent with its whole strategy (Grosspietsch, & Swan, 2009). Another of Zara’s competitive advantage is its low advertising costs. Particularly, it is its firm belief that advertising is not always the best way to attract customers. For this reason, Zara counterbalances such as deficient with using the word-to-mouth method as a mean of gaining publicity. Specifically, it hires trained sellers that have a certain code of conduct that should abide which refers to the way in which they should communicate with employees. Being gentle, kind, and asking customers’ feedback is one of the main tasks of salesmen. This combined with Zara’s strategy to constantly open up many stores in central areas which are elegant and appealing and making constant renovation helped the company to create a unique experience to customers who are more likely to disseminate their positive view to others; hence increasing the customer base of Zara and building strong relationships with its customers (Kalb, 2016). This is highly facilitated, as it is mentioned by the “fast fashion” that runs Zara since it creates loyal customers to the brand that are committed to it. Respectively, centralization is another competitive advantage of Zara as all the decision is taken from the "Cube." This enables Zara to make quick and effective decisions by giving direct solutions to the problems that emerged. From this perspective, such a system assists the company to maintain control over its activities and to correspond to market needs without intervention from other headquarters. Finally, concerning the financial management of the company, it should be noted that the company maintains a good state concerning its interest obligations and have many opportunities to generate cash flow from its operation and from shareholders as well. Its only disadvantage is its long-term investment which is very high. In any case, the financial statements of the company showed that Zara is a solid company that has many opportunities for growth based on its financial state (Cui, 2012).

3. The role of Information Technology in Zara’s success

An important role in Zara’s successful strategy played the Information Technology that is applied to facilitate decisions related to the product distribution, the inventory’s control, the stores ordering system and the investigations of customer preferences and market trends (Weill, Subramani, & Broadbent, 2002). Respectively, to be able to predict the new trends as well as the customer demands, Zara puts a great focus on extensive market research by using the most up-to-date software programs, Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs) systems that edit the data given by customers’ feedbacks, the data relating to daily sales, the customers’ features and the market trends. At this point, it is imperative to refer that the company coordinates with R & D stores so as to analyze consumer behavior (Tiwari, 2011). With these practices,

Zara's designers are facilitated in the design process and generally to the decision regarding the style of each new collection. Respectively, the latest software programs used by the company, such as C-Design, Corel Draw, Graphics Suit help designers to be quick in their designs through developed computers which assist designers in manufacturing the finished product (Vaish, 2017). This means that Zara's software programs have some basic patterns and based on them and the market research data that retrieve from its database, they can make the proper amendments. Furthermore, due to the contribution of this advanced technology, Zara is aware of the quantities needed for each shop since those systems are able to predict the purchase dynamic of customers based on the number of residents and the customers' demand. What's more, information technology helps the company to determine its inventory costs as all stores are equipped with POS that is linked with the "Cube" in which all the information is directly received along with its warehouse inventories.

4. SWOT analysis

In order to provide a deep insight into Zara's efficacy strategy, it is important to construct a SWOT analysis with the view to highlight the strength, the weak points, the opportunities and the threats that may face the business. So, the company's strengths are its unique designs, its strong presence in Europe, the cost leadership strategy applied, its efficient distribution system, its brand value, its attractive stores with design advantages, the information technology used, and the short lead time it takes to deliver its new products. On the other hand, its weaknesses are the lack of advertising, the low safety inventory stocks, and its generalized collection. Its opportunities lie in the e-commerce stores and especially its penetration into the online market, the growing market potential, generally, and its expansion into new emerging markets. Its threats are the local and global competitors and the fact that Zara does not have shops in the shop but merely its own shops (Bhasin, 2018).

5. Limitations and Zara's pitfalls

The challenges and the pitfalls that Zara should take into account stem also from its operating system and specifically from the fact that Zara used an internal software and hardware program (POS-Point-of-Sales) which is not supported by traditional technology companies, such as Microsoft. This means that it is very difficult to be changed as its whole IT programs relied on the capabilities of POS terminals to disseminate important data to the "Cube." Another challenge lies in the fact that the detection of inventories is time-consuming and not precise concerning the inventories existed in the stores as Zara's employees should investigate the number of inventories and make census. So, it is advisable to be established a system in which the "Cube" will be notified of the inventories in shops in real time. Furthermore, another inefficient is the lack of networking capabilities. Particularly, the POS which is established in each shop does not connect with other terminals but only with the "Cube," hence making difficult the communication between the shops and the "Cube." Also, Zara lacks in Chief Information Officer but rather, all the relevant decisions are taken by a committee at Zara making the final decision difficult to be taken in the IT sector. Last but not least, Zara has a strong presence in Europe but very little in other countries. This will be a disadvantage in the long-run as the competition is really aggressive and operating only in such markets may bring the risk of getting saturated. However, expanding Zara in other countries is not an easy venture due to its centralized logistics and its restricted distribution centers, basically to Spain and Portugal (Francis, n.d.).

6. Recommendations

One suggestion to be solved such potential pitfalls might be the integration of a new IT system or more specifically the improvement of the already existed IT system which should be done gradually so as to properly integrate within the company's policies and avoid extra costs that might harm the financial sustainability of the company (Faraj, 2010). Apart from that, concerning its marketing strategy, Zara should rethink advertising as a great mean of gaining more customers since the market is becoming even more competitive and if Zara wants to expand its activities to other countries, then increasing the advertising

budget might be necessary. Another recommendation for Zara might be to expand the range of its designer. This is really important since Zara “fast fashion” requires people that are creative and flexible in their minds so as to adapt to the latest style of clothes. Also, Zara could broaden its channel of production so that it improves its operation technology and increase its distribution centers so as to retain the fast and effective delivery system that already has by simultaneously exploiting the retailers’ knowledge and experiences (Zara Case Study, n.d.). Finally, a preferable market for expansion may be the Middle East since Zara has a small presence there but many opportunities to enhance its brand positioning.

Conclusion

Taking everything into account, I would like to point out that Zara managed to succeed in the very competitive market of the fashion industry by launching an innovative business model that involves its agile supply chains that support its just-in-time strategy, its in-house production, its vertical integration system and of course its up-to-date information technology. Having all the aforementioned competitive advantages, Zara was able to recognize and correspond quickly to the market demands and customer preferences by thinking unconventionally.

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